

Case Report

Bilateral Idiopathic Proximal Tibiofibular Joint Dislocation: An Extremely Rare Cause of Lateral Knee Pain – Case Report and Literature Review

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ABSTRACT

Objective: Proximal tibiofibular joint (PTFJ) dislocation is one of the causes of lateral knee pain and is very rare. The bilateral form, and especially when idiopathic, is even more uncommon. This study presents the first true bilateral idiopathic PTFJ dislocation reported in the literature. The case report also includes a literature review and provides discussion on surgical approaches.

Methods: A 16-year-old female patient presented with lateral pain, clicking sound, and a feeling of discomfort in both knees during flexion and extension. No history of trauma or connective tissue disease was identified. On physical examination, tenderness and abnormal movement were observed in both fibular heads. Peroneal nerve examination was normal. Direct radiographs revealed asymmetry at the level of the fibular heads, and MRI showed increased fluid accumulation and minimal synovial changes in both proximal tibiofibular joints. Since symptoms persisted despite previous conservative treatments, surgical intervention was planned. To preserve the functional stability of the joint, a tunnel was opened from the lateral posterior of the fibula to the anteromedial of the tibia, and fixation was performed using a suture-button suspension system.

Results: Postoperative radiographs confirmed proper alignment and joint stability. The patient achieved full recovery without pain, instability, or neurological deficit at the 12-month follow-up.

Conclusion: Bilateral idiopathic PTFJ dislocation is an extremely rare condition that is difficult to diagnose and requires a high degree of clinical suspicion. Detailed physical examination and advanced imaging methods such as MRI play a critical role in diagnosis. While conservative treatment may be effective in stable and neurologically asymptomatic cases, surgical intervention may be necessary in the presence of instability or recurrence. The suture-button technique may be an effective option due to its minimally invasive nature and advantage in preserving functional stability.

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Introduction

Proximal tibiofibular joint (PTFJ) dislocation is very rarely observed, and this joint contributes only minimally to the knee and ankle joints. According to Ogden's classification, dislocations can occur in four different types, with anterolateral being the most common. (Ogden, 1974)

PTFJ dislocation is a rare cause of anterolateral knee pain. In most reported cases, dislocations are due to trauma or connective tissue disorders; however, even these are quite rare. (Ogden, 1974; Dervin et al., 1997) To the best of our knowledge, a bilateral PTFJ dislocation case has been reported only once in the literature, but that patient was a professional ballet dancer. (Dervin et al., 1997) However, given the patient's exposure to intense physical activity, it is unlikely that this case represents a truly idiopathic condition.

For these reasons, as our patient had no trauma, athletic history, or connective tissue disease, we consider this case to represent the first true bilateral idiopathic dislocation reported in the literature.

In our case of bilateral idiopathic PTFJ dislocation, we aimed to achieve functional stability and reduce implant failure by using the suture-button technique. In our case report, a review of the literature is also presented along with current treatment methods and surgical procedures.

Case Presentation

A 16-year-old female patient presented with pain on the lateral sides of both knees, clicking sounds, and especially a feeling of discomfort during flexion and extension. The patient was particularly disturbed by the sound and the sensation of discomfort. She was not an athlete and had no history of trauma or systemic connective tissue disease.

On physical examination, there was tenderness over both fibular heads, and abnormal movement or separation greater than 1 cm was observed in the proximal tibiofibular joint; a clicking sound was heard during movement, but there was no swelling in either knee.

Varus and valgus stress tests and Lachman tests were normal. Motor and sensory examination of the peroneal nerve was normal.

On direct radiographs, asymmetry was observed at the level of the fibular heads. (Figure 1) MRI revealed increased fluid accumulation and minimal synovial changes in both proximal tibiofibular joints. (Figure 2)

Since the symptoms persisted despite previous conservative treatments, surgical intervention was planned. In order to preserve the functional stability of the joint, a tunnel was opened from the lateral posterior of the fibula to the anteromedial of the tibia, and fixation was performed with a suture-button. The suture-button suspension system was preferred because it is a simple, easily applicable, and stable method.

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Figure 1. Direct radiographs of the knees. (a) Anteroposterior view of both knees. (b) Lateral view of both knees.

Figure 2. Axial MRI images of the right knee showing increased fluid and minimal synovial changes at the proximal tibiofibular joint. (a) Superior axial slice. (b) Inferior axial slice. Similar findings were also observed in the left knee.

Surgical Procedure: Under general anesthesia, following proper sterilization and draping, the left fibular head was first palpated, and a 5 cm oblique incision was made from posterolateral to anteromedial through the area between the fibular head and neck. The layers were passed appropriately, and the peroneal nerve was identified and preserved. (Figure 3)

Then, under fluoroscopic control, a guide wire was advanced from the posterolateral part of the fibula to the anteromedial part of the tibia. Subsequently, a tunnel was created, and with the knee in 90 degrees of flexion, fixation was achieved using a suture-button through the tunnel, ensuring appropriate tension. (Figure 4)

Then, the same procedure was applied to the contralateral knee, and the operation was completed.

Postoperative Rehabilitation: Peroneal nerve functions were preserved in the postoperative period. The patient was mobilized with full weight-bearing after surgery, and no restriction was applied in terms of joint mobilization. The patient was advised to gradually increase joint range of motion. In the early postoperative period, significant bilateral improvement was observed in complaints of pain, instability, and clicking. At the 12-month follow-up, the patient had no pain or instability on physical examination.

Figure 3. Intraoperative image showing identification and protection of the peroneal nerve.

Figure 4. Post-fixation intraoperative fluoroscopic image showing suture-button placement from the fibula to the tibia.

Discussion

Bilateral idiopathic PTFJ dislocation is extremely rare and therefore difficult to diagnose; in our case, the diagnosis was delayed for three years. It is a diagnosis that should be kept in mind in patients with lateral knee pain and requires a high index of suspicion. Diagnosis is mostly made clinically, but MRI is mainly used to rule out other pathologies and to evaluate capsular damage.

Only one bilateral case has been reported in the literature, and that patient was a ballet dancer treated conservatively. (Dervin et al., 1997) Although this case was reported as idiopathic, the patient was exposed to significant mechanical stress. In our case, although bilateral dislocation was also present, there was no history of trauma, hypermobility, or sports activity, supporting that our case represents the first true bilateral idiopathic dislocation. Our patient was treated with the suture-button technique.

In the literature, treatment options include conservative follow-up and activity modification, physical therapy, anatomical ligament reconstructions, arthrodesis, or rigid screw fixation. (Krause & Parekh, 2006; Horst & LaPrade, 2010; van den Bekerom et al., 2011; Costigan et al., 2015; Cantillo et al., 2025; Sarac et al., 2025)

The suture-button suspension technique has recently gained attention as a method aimed at preserving the functional system. (Price et al., 2020; McGahan et al., 2021; Kruckeberg et al., 2017) Rigid screw fixation limits joint motion and requires hardware removal. (Krause & Parekh, 2006) Anatomical ligament reconstructions provide natural kinematics but are technically demanding procedures. (Horst & LaPrade, 2010)

In our case, the suture-button suspension system was preferred because it is simple, easy to apply, and has the potential to preserve physiological movement. Studies have shown that this method offers good functional outcomes, low complication rates, and biomechanical stability comparable to screw fixation. (Costigan et al., 2015; Price et al., 2020; Kruckeberg et al., 2017)

Postoperative rehabilitation after PTFJ surgery is not clearly defined in the literature; no standard protocols have been described, and most case reports provide little to no information regarding rehabilitation. Except for one study involving anatomical reconstruction that recommended non-weight-bearing for six weeks followed by progressive strengthening and return to sports, (Krause & Parekh, 2006) no consistent protocol exists. In our case, after suture-button fixation, we allowed full weight-bearing ambulation and did not restrict joint mobilization.

In the early postoperative period, significant improvement in symptoms was observed, and at the 12-month follow-up, the patient reported no pain, instability, or other adverse complaints. Consistent with the literature, our patient experienced early recovery, successful functional outcomes, and early return to sports.

Conclusion

This study presents the first true bilateral idiopathic PTFJ dislocation case reported in the literature. PTFJ dislocation, whether idiopathic or secondary to another cause, is an extremely rare condition and should be considered in the differential diagnosis of lateral knee pain in adolescents. In cases where conservative treatment fails, the suture-button technique emerges as an effective and reliable surgical option.

Declaration of conflicting interests

No conflict of interest was declared by the authors.

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Ethical approval

Ethical approval was not required for this single case report. Written informed consent for publication was obtained from the patient.

Institutional Review Board

Information about the study was given to the personnel and informed consent for this study was obtained

References

- Cantillo, C. F., et al. (2025). Tibial shaft fracture with knee and proximal tibiofibular dislocation: Case report. *J ISAKOS*, 10, 1-6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jisako.2025.100902>
- Costigan, W. M., Tennyson, J., Bonasia, D. E., & Amendola, A. (2015). Traumatic proximal tibiofibular dislocation: A systematic review and biomechanical comparison of surgical techniques. *Knee Surgery, Sports Traumatology, Arthroscopy*, 23(10), 2884-2890. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00167-014-3017-8>
- Dervin, G. F., Papp, S., & McKee, N. (1997). Bilateral proximal tibiofibular joint subluxation in a ballet dancer: A case report. *The American Journal of Sports Medicine*, 25(3), 414-416. <https://doi.org/10.1177/036354659702500323>
- Horst, P. K., & LaPrade, R. F. (2010). Anatomic reconstruction of chronic symptomatic anterolateral proximal tibiofibular joint instability. *Knee Surgery, Sports Traumatology, Arthroscopy*, 18(11), 1452-1455. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00167-010-1190-3>
- Krause, D. A., & Parekh, S. G. (2006). Proximal tibiofibular joint instability. *Foot and Ankle Clinics*, 11(3), 627-637. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fcl.2006.05.008>
- Kruckeberg, B. M., Cinque, M. E., Moatshe, G., Marchetti, D., DePhillipo, N. N., Chahla, J., & LaPrade, R. F. (2017). Proximal tibiofibular joint instability and treatment approaches: A systematic review of the literature. *Arthroscopy: The Journal of Arthroscopic & Related Surgery*, 33(9), 1743-1751. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arthro.2017.03.028>
- McGahan, P. J., et al. (2021). Revision proximal tibiofibular joint reconstruction for recurrent instability. *Arthroscopy Techniques*, 10, e2193-e2199. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eats.2021.03.011>
- Ogden, J. A. (1974). Subluxation and dislocation of the proximal tibiofibular joint. *The Journal of Bone and Joint Surgery. American Volume*, 56(1), 145-154.
- Price, A., et al. (2020). Cortical button fixation for proximal tibiofibular instability. *Arthroscopy Techniques*, 9(11), e1649-e1654. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eats.2020.08.005>
- Sarac, N., Burger, J., & Miller, T. (2025). Proximal tibiofibular joint instability: Outcomes following reconstruction with biceps femoris and iliotibial band autografts with suture tape augmentation. *Journal of Clinical Orthopaedics and Trauma*, 64, 102942. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcot.2025.102942>
- van den Bekerom, M. P. J., Weir, A., van der Flier, R. E., & van Dijk, C. N. (2011). Surgical stabilization of the proximal tibiofibular joint: A new technique. *Knee Surgery, Sports Traumatology, Arthroscopy*, 19(8), 1203-1206. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00167-011-1419-6>